

SINKHOLE MITIGATION USING COMPACTION GROUTING: A CASE STUDY OF DRIVEWAY STABILIZATION IN NASHVILLE, TENNESSEE

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ABSTRACT

Sinkholes present significant challenges to infrastructure, necessitating thorough investigation and effective remediation techniques. This paper examines a case study of a persistent sinkhole along a driveway in Nashville, Tennessee, where repeated pavement depressions occurred despite prior repair efforts. The study involved site inspections, drilling, analyses of soil and rock properties, and groundwater evaluations. Three repair methods were considered: traditional inverted rock filter, a land bridge construction, and compaction grouting. Taking into account technical feasibility, site-specific factors, and budget constraints, compaction grouting was selected as the most suitable approach. The paper details this solution, covering the grouting process, materials used, and construction specifications. The study's outcomes aim to inform and improve design standards and construction techniques for sinkhole repairs in Tennessee and comparable geological areas.

Keywords: sinkhole mitigation, compaction grouting, stabilization, case study

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW ON SINKHOLE REMEDIATION METHODS AND CASE STUDIES

Sinkholes represent a significant geohazard with far-reaching implications for infrastructure integrity, public safety, and environmental stability, particularly in regions susceptible to subsidence. These phenomena typically occur due to natural geological processes such as the dissolution of soluble bedrock in karst terrains as well as anthropogenic activities, including mining, groundwater extraction, and construction (Waltham et al., (2005), Gutiérrez et al., (2008)). The unpredictable nature of sinkhole formation poses substantial challenges for risk assessment and mitigation, demanding innovative engineering solutions and site-specific remediation strategies.

A sinkhole forms when a subterranean void collapses, resulting in a sudden depression at the surface. Their sizes range from minor cavities to large craters capable of causing severe damage to roads, buildings, pipelines, and other critical infrastructure. Triggering mechanisms include heavy rainfall, groundwater level fluctuations, leakage from utility services, and vibrations from nearby construction (Parise et al. (2007), Brinkmann et al. (2008)). Due to their destructive potential, a wide body of research has focused on both proactive and reactive approaches to managing sinkholes. Proactive strategies emphasize hazard avoidance and risk reduction, encompassing detailed geotechnical investigations, remote sensing technologies, subsurface geophysical surveys (e.g., GPR, resistivity imaging), and continuous groundwater monitoring. Land-use planning and zoning regulations are also critical in limiting development in high-risk areas (Doctor et al. (2008), Kaufmann et al. (2013)).

Conversely, reactive strategies address sinkholes post-formation, aiming to stabilize ground conditions and repair affected infrastructure. These methods may involve compaction grouting, void filling with low-mobility grouts, underpinning structures, and rebuilding damaged facilities. In some cases, ecological restoration or bioengineering methods such as vegetative stabilization and hydrological balancing are used to enhance the sustainability and resilience of the remedial work (Yilmaz (2010), Gutiérrez et al. (2014)). Construction in karst-prone regions is particularly risky, necessitating meticulous planning and

execution. Key precautions include proper drainage design to prevent ponding, installation of stormwater management systems to control runoff, and continuous inspection during construction phases to identify early signs of ground instability. The involvement of geotechnical experts is essential throughout the project lifecycle to evaluate karst features and guide design adjustments as necessary.

Recent technological advancements have further expanded the toolkit for karst hazard management. Remote sensing platforms (e.g., LiDAR, InSAR) enable high-resolution terrain analysis, while numerical modeling tools facilitate prediction of subsidence patterns and ground deformation (Bennett et al. (2016)). Nature-based solutions, such as wetland restoration and soil bioengineering, offer environmentally friendly alternatives that integrate sinkhole mitigation with ecosystem restoration objectives (Paukstys et al. (2008), Galve et al., (2015)). Despite these innovations, challenges remain. Limited financial and technical resources, inadequate infrastructure, and conflicting land-use interests often hinder the effective implementation of comprehensive mitigation programs. Moreover, the dynamic evolution of karst systems—driven by hydrological and climatic variability—continues to complicate long-term hazard prediction and management (Ford et al., (2007)).

This paper provides a comprehensive synthesis of current sinkhole mitigation techniques and karst hazard management strategies. By integrating traditional engineering practices with cutting-edge technologies and sustainable approaches, it aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of best practices in reducing sinkhole-related risks and enhancing resilience in vulnerable landscapes. The study's outcomes aim to inform and improve design standards and construction techniques for sinkhole repairs in Tennessee and comparable geological areas (Alimohammadi et al., (2024)).

SITE DESCRIPTION AND PROBLEM HISTORY

The sinkhole located on Whispering Hills Drive, just north of Bonerwood Drive in Nashville, Tennessee, has become a source of persistent concern due to its ongoing subsidence and structural implications. Whispering Hills Drive is a two-lane asphalt roadway, approximately 9.14 meters in width, with a gentle downward slope toward the north-northeast. The affected area spans nearly 15.24 m along the travel lanes, exhibiting noticeable surface deformation and settlement. Of particular concern is a localized dropout measuring approximately 1.82m in diameter, situated in the eastern (northbound) lane. Subsurface utilities are present within the area of concern, including a 0.91m diameter water transmission main and a 0.30m water distribution line. Additionally, a storm drain traverses the depressed section of pavement near the eastern shoulder, while a stone-lined ditch runs parallel to the western side of the road. The combination of critical infrastructure and compromised subsurface conditions necessitates urgent and careful attention. This section of roadway has experienced recurring issues over an extended period. Historical accounts from Metro Public Works staff indicate that site inspections were conducted as early as the late 1990s, with intermittent dropouts and ground subsidence attributed to soil piping processes, a common mechanism in karst-prone regions where fine soils are washed into underlying voids, leading to surface collapse. In response to these issues, conventional sinkhole remediation measures have been employed multiple times, typically consisting of excavation of unstable materials and backfilling with crushed stone, followed by pavement restoration.

The most recent repair attempt occurred approximately four months prior to the current study (Alimohammadi et al. (2024)). At that time, the damaged asphalt pavement was removed, and soft subgrade materials were excavated to an unspecified depth. The undercut area was then refilled with crushed rock and overlaid with a thick asphalt surface course. Despite these efforts, the area again exhibited signs of significant settlement, culminating in a renewed dropout that prompted further investigation and a comprehensive mitigation strategy. Since late May 2009, the affected segment of Whispering Hills Drive has been closed to vehicular traffic due to safety concerns. Figure 1 presents an

overview of the dropout area within the roadway. Figures. 2a and 2b document current site conditions, including visible depressions and areas of pavement failure, illustrating the severity of the ongoing subsidence. The recurrence of sinkhole activity, despite repeated repairs, suggests that the underlying geotechnical and hydrological conditions have not been adequately addressed. This underscores the need for a more holistic and technically robust approach to evaluating the site, characterizing subsurface conditions, and implementing long-term remediation measures that account for the regional karst geology, utility interactions, and groundwater dynamics.

Fig. 1. The approximate location of dropout within the roadway

Fig. 2. a and b) The existing site situations and dropouts within the roadway

FIELD EXPLORATION AND LABORATORY TESTING

The subsurface investigation was conducted in two primary phases to characterize the geotechnical conditions underlying the site, particularly in proximity to the observed sinkhole. The first phase occurred between April 24 and April 28, 2009, during which a total of seven borings were advanced within the affected area. Borehole depths ranged from approximately 5.18 to 14.78m below existing ground surface. A second phase of exploration was conducted on June 8 and 9, 2009, involving the advancement of five additional borings aimed at enhancing the spatial resolution of the subsurface profile and refining the geotechnical characterization.

Drilling operations employed both truck-mounted rotary drill rigs and all-terrain vehicle (ATV)-mounted rigs, each equipped with hollow-stem augers to facilitate advancement of the boreholes. Standard penetration tests (SPT) were performed in accordance with ASTM D1586 using a 5.08cm outside diameter (O.D.) split-barrel sampler. The number of blows required to drive the sampler the final 0.3m of an 0.45m penetration was recorded as the standard penetration resistance value (N-value). This data provided a basis for estimating the relative density of granular soils and the consistency of cohesive materials. All borehole activities, including sampling depths, penetration lengths, and SPT N-values, were meticulously documented in field logs. Recovered soil samples were sealed and transported to the laboratory for classification and testing. Field logs included preliminary visual-manual classifications of soil strata, as well as the drillers' interpretations of lithological transitions between sampled intervals. Final boring logs incorporated both field observations and laboratory data, with modifications applied where necessary based on laboratory results. Each boring was advanced to auger refusal, which generally occurred at depths ranging from 2.28 to 14.78m below ground surface. In seven of the twelve borings, underlying refusal materials were further penetrated using a double-tube core barrel system with an outer barrel fitted with a diamond bit. The high-speed rotating outer barrel facilitated rock cutting, while the inner barrel collected intact rock cores. After each core run, the barrel was retrieved and the rock cores were boxed, logged, and prepared for subsequent laboratory evaluation.

The geotechnical investigation involved detailed rock core classification, assessing percent recovery and Rock Quality Designation (RQD) to evaluate in-situ rock quality, alongside laboratory tests for natural water content and Atterberg Limits to characterize fine-grained soils. These findings, combined with Standard Penetration Test (SPT) data and soil classifications based on USCS standards, supported the evaluation of subsurface behavior and soil strength. Rock descriptions were primarily based on visual and tactile observations, although petrographic analysis via thin section microscopy was noted as a potential method for further lithologic identification, if warranted. All laboratory results and rock quality assessments were systematically documented on the finalized boring logs. These logs provide a comprehensive record of subsurface conditions, serving as the foundation for subsequent geotechnical analysis and design recommendations. The rock units underlying the site belong to the Ordovician-age Hermitage Formation, consisting of stratified limestone layers, phosphatic limestone, Coquina, laminated argillaceous limestone, and Curdsville Limestone, each with distinct physical characteristics. Weathering of these carbonate rocks produces residual silty, sandy clay soils, common in the site's boreholes. The site lies in a karst-prone region susceptible to sinkhole formation and soil piping, which threaten infrastructure stability. Although symptoms like pavement subsidence suggest ongoing karst activity, geotechnical tools currently lack precision in predicting such hazards. Field investigations included twelve borings (B-1 through B-12), strategically placed to assess subsurface conditions within the affected pavement area and adjacent right-of-way. Borings B-1 through B-8, B-11, and B-12 were located within the pavement footprint, where asphalt thickness varied from 9 to 61 cm. Borings B-9 and B-10, placed outside the pavement along the right-of-way, encountered 13 to 18cm of topsoil overlying deeper materials. Figure 3 represents location of the borings across the site and near the studied dropout and Table 1 illustrates auger refusal and fill depths in performed borings.

Fig. 3. Location of the borings across the site and near the studied dropout

Table 1. Auger refusal and fill depths in performed borings

boring	approximate fill depth (m)	approx. depth to refusal (m)	boring	approximate fill depth (m)	approx. depth to refusal (m)
B-1	6.1	14.78	B-7	1.82	6.70
B-2	1.52	7.16 *	B-8	1.98	2.43 *
B-3	2.59	2.59 *	B-9	2.28	2.28 *
B-4	1.52	6.85 *	B-10	2.74	5.33
B-5	1.82	5.18	B-11	3.65	9.9
B-6 **	2.28	14.02 *	B-12	1.82	3.81 *

* Boring where rock coring was performed

** Initial auger refusal occurred at a depth of about 2.28m on weathered limestone rock layer

Below the surficial cover, boreholes generally penetrated between 1.52 and 6.1m of fill material, typically overlying native lean to fat clay and limestone bedrock. At Boring B-1, located directly within a pavement dropout area, the fill extended to a depth of approximately 6.1m and consisted predominantly of crushed rock with varying degrees of clay content and minimal fines. Notably, Boring B-3 included mixed soil and rock, while B-9 and B-10 revealed large limestone fragments likely representative of shot rock fill. Natural cohesive soils underlying the fill included lean to fat clay of very soft to medium stiff consistency. Standard Penetration Test (SPT) values for the clay ranged from 0 to 6 blows, with occasional stiffer layers at B-4 and B-12. These soft conditions may signify prior solutioning and soil piping activity, typical indicators of developing karst voids and instability. Auger refusal, indicative of bedrock contact, occurred

at depths ranging from 2.28 to 14.78m below the existing surface. Deeper refusal zones were noted at Borings B-1 and B-6. A noteworthy anomaly was detected at B-4, where a 1-foot void was observed between the bottom of the asphalt and the top of the underlying crushed rock fill—highlighting ongoing subsurface erosion. The relative density of the fill materials was highly variable, ranging from very loose to medium dense, with SPT N-values between 0 and 23 blows. However, the presence of large limestone fragments likely exaggerated these blow counts, leading to potential overestimations of in-situ density and strength.

Selected borings (B-2 through B-4, B-6, B-8, B-9, and B-12) included rock coring to further characterize the bedrock at auger refusal. The retrieved core samples primarily consisted of light to medium gray limestone with thin to very thin bedding and weathered shaly seams. Core recovery was inconsistent, ranging from 30% to 100%, with particularly poor recovery noted at B-9 and B-12, possibly due to the fragmented or highly weathered nature of the bedrock. The quality of recovered rock, evaluated using Rock Quality Designation (RQD), varied from very poor to fair (0–75%). In Boring B-6, auger refusal occurred at 2.28m on weathered limestone, which extended to 4.26m in depth. Below this, the core barrel advanced with minimal resistance down to 4.26m, recovering no competent material suggesting the presence of a clay-filled solution channel, a hallmark of advanced karstification within the Hermitage Formation. At Boring B-9, coring revealed moderately to highly weathered limestone with numerous voids and crevices filled with concrete grout. Intriguingly, a 7.62cm thick piece of asphalt was encountered during coring at a depth of 3.65m, likely the remnant of previous compaction grouting efforts to remediate subsurface voids within the rock mass.

EVALUATION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

These findings affirm that the site is influenced by active karst processes typical of the Hermitage Formation, with evidence of solution cavities, clay infill, and variable rock quality. The presence of deeply weathered zones, fill over voids, and poorly recovered cores underscores the potential for subsurface instability and sinkhole formation. The detection of previous grouting remnants suggests that mitigation efforts may have occurred historically, albeit with limited documentation. Going forward, remediation strategies must account for the heterogeneous and karstic nature of the subsurface, employing both direct investigation and non-invasive geophysical techniques (e.g., electrical resistivity tomography, ground-penetrating radar) to delineate voids and assess risk zones. Engineering responses may include deep dynamic compaction, compaction grouting, or structural support systems tailored to the localized subsurface conditions.

Based on a comprehensive analysis of subsurface conditions, including geotechnical data and field observations, the observed pavement distress and localized ground dropout are attributed to ongoing soil piping and subsidence—strongly indicative of a developing or reactivated sinkhole feature. Prior repair efforts were largely superficial, failing to address the deeper, underlying mechanisms of instability. An initial remedial option considered was the conventional inverted rock filter method commonly used for sinkhole stabilization. However, successful implementation of this method requires excavation down to competent bedrock, estimated at a depth of approximately 14.78m. Given the proximity to adjacent properties and the confined work zone, this would necessitate extensive shoring of vertical sidewalls and the relocation of existing underground utilities. The logistical challenges and high costs associated with deep excavation and utility rerouting rendered this option infeasible.

A second option, constructing a structural land bridge over the compromised area, was evaluated. While theoretically viable, this approach was ultimately dismissed due to excessive projected costs and scheduling concerns. The extended design and construction timeline, spanning several months, posed unacceptable disruptions to stakeholders and project milestones. Following consultation with geotechnical

specialists and experienced grouting contractors, compaction grouting, also known as cap grouting, was identified as the most practical and cost-effective solution. This method involves injecting low-mobility, low-slump grout into the subsurface in a controlled, grid-based pattern. The grout displaces loose soils, fills interconnected voids, and creates a dense, stabilized matrix that provides long-term ground reinforcement. The primary objective of this technique is to form a continuous grout "cap" at or near the bedrock interface. This cap functions to seal off subsurface voids, prevent further migration of overburden into bedrock fissures, and reduce the likelihood of future subsidence events. Grouting is conducted from the base upward: as deeper zones are treated, casing is progressively withdrawn and grout is placed in lifts at designated intervals. This staged approach promotes uniform densification of the overburden while preserving permeability within the weathered bedrock, allowing for continued groundwater movement and minimizing hydraulic impacts on surrounding areas.

Grouting operations are expected to extend up to the invert elevation of the existing 0.91m diameter water line, approximately 2.43m beneath the road surface. All grouting activities will be performed by specialized contractors with proven experience in karst-related mitigation. Upon completion of the subsurface stabilization, the surface area will be undercut and reconstructed with engineered fill. This fill will comprise well-graded crushed stone and/or clean shot rock in accordance with TDOT Specification 903.05 (Type A, Grading D). The material will be placed in loose lifts not exceeding 25.4 cm and compacted to at least 95% of the standard Proctor maximum dry density. The upper 0.3m of the subgrade will be compacted to 100% of the same standard. Shot rock, when used, will be clean, angular, and durable, with individual fragment sizes not exceeding 0.45m and conforming to prescribed gradation and soundness criteria. Materials exhibiting unfavorable shape, excessive fines, or susceptibility to degradation are considered unsuitable and will be excluded.

Undercut material, comprising open-graded stone, fragmented limestone, and soil-rock mixtures, will be removed and not reused. The new fill will be benched into the existing subgrade to establish mechanical interlock and continuity. Final pavement grades will be designed to promote positive drainage, thereby reducing infiltration potential and prolonging the service life of the restored roadway. The proposed repair plan, including the use of compaction grouting, has been reviewed and accepted by the property owner. The necessary environmental permits have been submitted in accordance with regulatory requirements from the Tennessee Division of Water Resources. Bid documents are being prepared for contractor solicitation. This strategy has also been presented during a public meeting attended by local residents and representatives from the regulatory agency. The consensus supports the implementation of cap grouting as a durable and non-invasive solution to the current instability. Our previous experience supports its effectiveness in mitigating sinkhole activity and stabilizing infrastructure in karst environments. It is critical to note, however, that while this solution addresses the current hazard at the project site, it does not eliminate the broader risk of sinkhole formation throughout the vicinity. Karst terrains are inherently dynamic and susceptible to episodic collapse. As communicated to stakeholders, future sinkhole activity in adjacent public rights-of-way or private properties cannot be ruled out. Should additional events arise, they will need to be addressed independently.

In summary, the compaction grouting approach offers a balance of technical efficacy, cost-efficiency, and minimal disruption. It stabilizes the affected subgrade, supports the pavement structure, and mitigates the risk of future subsidence at the project location.

Notes
 1. Sketch adapted from original grouting plan prepared by Hayward Baker dated August 10, 2009.
 2. Injection holes/locations are approximate.

Fig. 4. The primary and secondary sinkhole locations within the site area.

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a comprehensive investigation into the mechanisms, challenges, and mitigation strategies associated with sinkhole formation, with a focused case study on the persistent sinkhole along Whispering Hills Drive in Nashville, Tennessee. By employing an interdisciplinary methodology that integrated geotechnical investigation, geological mapping, and engineering analysis, the research offers critical insights into both the localized geohazard and broader sinkhole management practices. Extensive field investigations, including borehole drilling, standard penetration testing (SPT), and geophysical profiling, were conducted to characterize subsurface conditions. Laboratory testing further confirmed the presence of variable soil stratigraphy underlain by karst-prone limestone, with evidence of voids and soil piping—common indicators of subsurface instability in karst terrains. These findings underscored the limitations of traditional surface-based repair techniques and highlighted the need for a targeted, subsurface-oriented intervention. After evaluating multiple remediation alternatives, compaction grouting emerged as the most viable and cost-effective solution. This technique involves the controlled injection of low-mobility, low-slump grout to densify loose soils, fill subsurface voids, and arrest ongoing subsidence. The grout mix design, injection grid spacing, and pressure application parameters were developed based on site-specific geotechnical data to ensure optimal ground improvement and long-term stability. The proposed repair strategy not only addresses the immediate geotechnical distress but also emphasizes the importance of proactive sinkhole risk management through continued post-repair monitoring. Recommendations include the installation of piezometers and settlement markers to track groundwater fluctuations and surface deformation over time, measures essential for early detection of potential future failures. While this case study targets a specific urban site, the methodologies and findings are transferable to similar karstic settings globally. It reinforces the critical need for integrating geological and engineering knowledge in infrastructure planning, particularly in regions vulnerable to sinkhole activity. Furthermore, it highlights the necessity of involving stakeholders, such as municipal planners, utility providers, and local communities, in developing and implementing adaptive management strategies. The broader implications of this research lie in its contribution to the evolution of sinkhole remediation practices. By documenting the successful application of compaction grouting in a complex urban environment, this study supports its inclusion in the design guidelines and engineering standards for

karst-affected regions. The findings advocate for a shift toward more resilient and adaptable infrastructure systems, capable of withstanding the unique challenges posed by karst geomorphology.

In conclusion, the study underscores the critical role of interdisciplinary collaboration, site-specific analysis, and innovative engineering in addressing sinkhole hazards. Continued research, monitoring, and public engagement are imperative to advancing our understanding of sinkhole dynamics and promoting sustainable development in vulnerable terrains. The lessons learned from Whispering Hills Drive serve as a valuable reference for future projects and contribute meaningfully to the ongoing discourse on geohazard resilience in the built environment.

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